

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE CHANNELS OF PRODUCT DISTRIBUTION IN MARKETING

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Abstract. *This article examines the distribution of goods, sales promotion, establishing contacts, bringing the goods to the consumer in accordance with their requirements, conducting negotiations, organizing the movement of goods, financing and assuming risk, and the length, breadth and number of levels of distribution channels.*

Keywords: *medicine, distribution, consumer, pharmaceutical, product, social, political, development, promotion.*

Introduction. The healthcare sector is becoming one of the most important sectors of the modern economy. This is not only the medical sector, but also enterprises and sectors that produce and supply pharmaceuticals in many respects as a separate type of activity are gaining great importance. The pharmaceutical industry worldwide is the most important socially significant sector that ensures the sustainable development of the human healthcare system. This is because the healthcare system, as a separate area of social policy, is primarily aimed at preventing diseases or detecting and treating them at the initial stages.

Analysis of literature on the topic Scientific and theoretical aspects of improving marketing activities in the pharmaceutical market have been studied by scientists such as A. Balashov [8], Y.N. Kovalnogov. Scientists such as Wigglesworth, K., Zelcer, J. have described the behavior of customers of pharmaceutical companies. Foreign scientists have also been invited to study problems in the pharmaceutical market. O.A. Vasnetsova, Kareva N.I., V.I. Krikov, S.A. Lagunova, E.A. Maksimkina, V.I. Prokopishin, M.V. Ryzhkova, A.Yu. Yudanov, M. Brown, N. Evanson, JE Fincham, RA Gosselin, MC Smith, JB Thomas, AI Wertheimer contributed their work. Among the scientists of our country, Bobbojonov d.Saipova D.T., Ilyasova K.A., Yunuskhoev A.A., A.Alimov focused on pharmaceutical marketing.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. Consists of:

The purpose of our scientific research in the market of pharmaceutical products is to suggest ways to develop marketing activities of wholesale enterprises in the drug market, including methods of sales promotion.

In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and performed in the article:

Revealing the characteristics of marketing activities in the pharmaceutical market;

Analysis of the activities of participants of the drug market in the city of Samarkand;

Analyzing marketing activities at "Biokosmik" LLC in the city of Samarkand;

Distribution channels consist of a set of intermediaries that take ownership of the goods or assist in the sale on the way from the manufacturer to the consumer. Intermediate links can be simple intermediaries, wholesalers, and retailers.

- The specific features of the pharmaceutical market of Samarkand region are revealed;
- The rules of marketing activities of wholesale intermediaries in the drug market have been revealed;
- The mechanism of managing wholesale and retail trade in the pharmaceutical market is disclosed;
- Methodical recommendations for product distribution and sales promotion have been developed in pharmaceutical trade.

Selling goods directly to the final consumer is carried out by offering goods in a retail enterprise - "merchandising", licensed trade - "franchising" and establishing direct contact with the consumer - "direct marketing". The use of intermediaries is such that, relying on their experience and high quality of work, they can offer the goods in the most appropriate form, thereby bringing more profit to the manufacturer. At the same time, an increase in the number of intermediaries can lead to an increase in the price of goods, a slowdown in turnover and, in general, an increase in the cost of the entire process of goods movement.

The fact is that in LLC "BIOCOSMIC" pharmaceutical products are produced in a narrow range that allows you to make the right choice based on your needs. The task of changing the assortment is assigned to intermediaries, through which they play a largely positive role in studying partnership relations and, on this basis, concluding agreements with manufacturers of goods. Among them, the most important are the functions of information, sales promotion, establishing contacts, bringing the goods to the consumer's requirements. Negotiations, organizing the movement of goods, financing and assuming risks. Distribution channels are characterized by their length, width and number of stages. The stages are the intermediate links of the movement of goods. In turn, the sum of the intermediate links forms the length of the distribution channel. In this case, the manufacturer of the goods is the initial link of the channel, and consumers are the final link of the channel.

A single-tier channel includes, in addition to the retailer and wholesaler, a small wholesaler. In trade practice, channels with a larger number of intermediate links may also be encountered, but they are not of great importance in organizing the movement of goods.

Today, the enterprise "BIOCOSMIC" LLC is organized in a four-tiered manner. A single-tier channel is usually called a direct marketing channel, since it consists of initial and final links, that is, there are no intermediate links. Direct selling has a growth trend, especially in countries with developed economies. This channel is almost not used in the sale of pharmaceutical products.

A two-tier channel has one intermediate link, usually a retailer. This type is widespread among manufacturers of food, agricultural products, building materials, etc. This type of channel is also almost absent in BIOCOSMIC LLC.

The three-tier channel is supplemented by a wholesaler along with the retailer. This channel is used by manufacturers of more complex household appliances, pharmaceuticals, and some types of food products. BIOCOSMIC LLC can be considered a representative of such a channel, but the large number of pharmaceuticals makes the channel even more complicated.

The four-tier channel, in addition to the retailer and wholesaler, also includes a small wholesaler. In trade practice, channels with a larger number of intermediate links may also occur,

but they do not play a significant role in organizing the movement of goods. Each distribution channel has its own organizational structure, and in this sense, the channel participant interacts with other links. However, the well-being of the “BIOCOSMIC” LLC enterprise itself, and especially its well-being, is largely a reflection of how competently the processes of sales and customer service are carried out at points. The productivity of each of its participants, taken separately, is determined by two factors:

- firstly, with the level of functioning of the entire distribution channel;
- secondly, the ability of this channel to compete with other channels producing wine and spirits.

The distribution channel selection process relies on optimizing efforts across space and time to first identify specific partners that can positively impact the product's direct-to-consumer movement.

In general, the number of intermediaries and their functions in the "producer-consumer" chain vary from product to product, from region to region, from country to country. Most channel participants only purchase and resell goods, while others tend to pay more attention to marketing activities. The experience of European countries indicates certain trends in the development and improvement of the distribution channel as a whole, including its individual elements. In a nutshell, their meaning is as follows:

- the number of intermediate links in the distribution channels is decreasing due to the improvement of the use of transport systems for the delivery of goods and the improvement of information transmission, as well as due to the decrease in the role of wholesale trade, instead of the strengthening of the position of the manufacturers of goods, who in many cases prove the possibility of performing the functions of wholesalers (also, the initiators of these routes may be retailers);

- increased control over the formation of price policy in distribution channels, large companies trying to create their own distribution systems against the aggressive policy of retail sales;

- Significant changes are taking place in the way people use their free and working time, which in turn is leading to a reassessment of aspects such as the use of rational and efficient methods of distribution channel sales technology, self-service, microprocessors (especially their programming capabilities), the development of supermarkets and shopping clubs that allow consumers to significantly save free time and at the same time provide convenience and service.

Improving product distribution includes providing accurate and timely information about products directly to consumers, and effectively using the media, television, and radio in this regard.

In addition, the competitiveness of the manufactured product must also be at a high level.

In “BIOCOSMICS” LLC, in addition to improving the quality and competitiveness of products manufactured by other enterprises, it is also important that the buyer has the ability to pay for the sale of goods. Therefore, demand is also called “satisfactory demand”.

Sales promotion is commercial and marketing activities aimed at increasing sales over a period of time, as well as the work of pharmaceutical employees in a pharmacy organization:

- stimulation of consumer demand;
- improving the quality of service;
- speeding up the process of goods circulation and sale of goods;
- positioning of the product/manufacturer's brand.

There are two activity blocks in the activity complex:

1) activities aimed at the end consumer of medicines and pharmacy products. They should encourage trial or repeat purchases, as well as increase the frequency of consumption of pharmacy products. The ultimate goal of these activities is to increase consumer activity;

2) pharmacy organizations as a member of the distribution network - measures aimed at promoting the distribution network. They are aimed at developing distribution, accelerating turnover and increasing sales.

Marketing activity aimed at the pharmacy organization is a set of measures aimed at promoting its sales, accelerating the turnover of goods and increasing the volume of sales. These measures include:

- Affiliate loyalty programs or loyalty programs based on cross-marketing. The buyer creates a bonus card with offers from the program's partners. For each purchase, he receives points on the card, which can be used as discounts for purchases or gifts from partners.

- motivation of employees of pharmaceutical organizations. Motivation is the process of external influence on an employee for the successful performance of a task or for effective work in general. There are internal and external incentives. External incentives are provided by distributors and / or manufacturers for certain volumes of drug sales. Internal incentives depend on the performance indicators of the pharmacy organization.

When buying a product, people intend to satisfy certain needs. Therefore, information about the quality indicators of the product is necessary. Entering the market is a responsible period for the company, and information about its products is not provided. The future consumer must receive the following information:

- availability of goods and place of sale;
- which needs are aimed at satisfaction;
- basic indicators of consumer value;
- Guarantees to protect customers in the event of dissatisfaction.

Methods of communicating information to prospective buyers:

- Advertisements (radio, television, written).
- Conducting exhibitions.
- Meetings through conventions and films.

Addressing uninformed buyers will stimulate their demand and encourage them to buy the product.

So, one of the main reasons for the formation of demand is to attract buyers to the product, to provide them with accurate and accurate information about the product, to attract the consumer with the appearance of the product, packaging, etc. Sales promotion is aimed at consumers who have a certain level of information about the product. Therefore, the task of the promotion policy is to arouse in them a desire to purchase the company's products in the future and to encourage them to stay in touch.

Demand generation activities are usually aimed at consumers and sellers. Incentives for consumers are intended to provide them with significant commercial benefits:

- a benefit based on the volume of purchases and regular contact;
- sale of goods for various forms of debt;
- distribution of samples free of charge with a view to purchasing goods in large quantities;
- free supply of goods for temporary use;
- acceptance of used goods under certain conditions;

- Showcase new products to potential buyers;
- organization of trips to enterprises producing goods;
- holding press conferences dedicated to the introduction of new products to the market;
- announcements on the radio, television and press about a sharp reduction in the price of goods.

The promotion policy for the products depends on the type of customers who buy them. It is intended to encourage intermediaries, to increase their activity and initiative, and to expand the circle of consumers. The policy of demand formation and sales promotion must correspond to the life stages of the product in the market and give appropriate content to each of them.

Personal selling / direct marketing

It represents the impact on a specific audience by order of the manufacturer or in accordance with the database created by him or by receiving feedback from a specific consumer. The essence of the method is to personalize the advertising message. It is customary to distinguish five traditional forms of direct marketing: direct mail marketing, catalog marketing, telemarketing (marketing by telephone, telecommunications technologies and database management systems for marketing purposes), television marketing (advertising on television, the use of specially developed commercial channels), transmission of commercial and advertising information, after reading which the consumer can order goods at competitive prices without leaving home), electronic commerce. This type of advertising is practically not used in a pharmacy organization.

Public relations - coordinating efforts to create a positive image of a particular product in the minds of consumers. The goal of promotion is to attract the attention of potential consumers without advertising costs.

Main means of promotion:

- speeches: participation of representatives of pharmaceutical manufacturers and pharmaceutical organizations at the opening of various events, etc.;
- events: organization of press conferences, seminars and anniversaries, participation in exhibitions, contests and contests, etc.;
- news: providing the media with positive news about the pharmaceutical organization and its employees (press releases);
- publications: annual reports, newsletters, brochures, magazine or newspaper articles, and other printed materials used as a means of influencing target markets;
- sponsorship: allocation of time, financial and material resources to support the organization of charitable, sports and other socially significant events;
- means of identification: use of the emblem (logo) of the pharmaceutical organization, writing paper with watermarks and other markings, corporate-style packaging materials, business cards, creating websites, developing and implementing a uniform style and design of buildings.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS.

The theoretical and practical research conducted allowed us to come to the following conclusions.

As a result of the research conducted, we at BIOCOSMIC LLC have developed a number of recommendations for product distribution and sales promotion, the content of which is as follows:

1. In order to be superior to competitors, it is desirable to introduce differentiation of orders for medicines, that is, separation by classifications. In particular, grouping drug products by order volume and repeat order is one way to meet customer needs.

2. Including forecasting and monitoring the demand for medicinal products We offer this as one of the ways to improve sales at BIOCOSMIC LLC.

3. It is necessary to further improve the system of incentives for buyers. For this, it is recommended to study advanced foreign and local experience. Another area of focus for BIOCOSMIC LLC is training and advanced training of personnel in marketing methods.

4. Since e-commerce currently accounts for a very small share of the turnover of BIOCOSMIC LLC, one of our recommendations is to develop network marketing and e-commerce.

5. Since BIOCOSMIC LLC is a young, newly formed enterprise, it is necessary to pay increased attention to developing a marketing strategy.

The implementation of these recommendations will serve to improve the drug distribution system at BIOCOSMIC LLC.

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